

Certificate

Valentyna NESTERENKO

for Participation in the International scientific conference

THE GREATEST HUMANKIND ACHIEVEMENTS
IN HEALTHCARE AND VETERINARY MEDICINE

February 7–8, 2024, Riga, the Republic of Latvia

Total: 15 hours – 0.5 ECTS credit

Roman Djakon,
Doctor of Engineering, Professor,
Academician, President of ISMA University
of Applied Sciences

Denis Djakon,
Doctor of Economics, Professor,
Rector of ISMA University
of Applied Sciences